

1: Introduction

Existing ASD diagnostic criteria may be limited when attempting to capture the full range of ASD phenotypes, often failing to assess symptoms commonly found in women. Historically, research on ASD reflects this gender imbalance. In 1943, Leo Kanner's *Autistic Disturbances of Affective Contact* studied eight cases of ASD in males compared to three cases in females. Similarly, Hans Asperger's 1944 study utilized exclusively male subjects to establish and describe Asperger's disorder (Kreiser and White 67, Rivet and Matson 958). Koenig and Tsatsanis report that diagnostic tools such as the Autism Diagnostic Interview (ADI), ADI-Revised (ADI-R), and Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule (ADOS) were curated and standardized based on a predominantly male sample with a male to female ratio of 3:1 (Rivet and Matson 958).

2: Background

2.1: Existing Gender Disparity

The lack of knowledge on the female ASD phenotype in comparison to the male phenotype is an emerging topic of research. Utilizing findings from existing research, multiple hypotheses regarding the disparity between male and female ASD diagnosis rates can be formed.

ASD diagnosis and evaluation tools are much more accurate for male patients than female patients, yielding much higher diagnostic rates for males as a result. As cited in Estrin et al., Young et al. report that clinical tools are optimized for the male ASD phenotype due to the disproportionate lack of research on females (Estrin, et al.). Mao et al., upon extracting data from 47 studies examining the relationship between gender and diagnosis, symptom expression, and impact of intervention, found that common treatment methods, such as Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) and Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT), resulted in significantly higher rates of improvement among males. They attribute this to the lack of externalized symptoms (delinquency, violence, or similar aggression, commonly observed in the male ASD phenotype) among females with ASD. They also connect this to a significant gender imbalance in ASD research samples, proposing that diagnostic and intervention tools have been inadvertently tailored to male presentations (Mao et al. 105).

Head et al. reports similar findings, suggesting that internalized symptoms among females with ASD are further complicated by social camouflage. Using the Friendship Questionnaire (FQ) to analyze gender differences' impact on interpersonal relationships, Head et al. found that female children with ASD (n = 25) scored significantly higher on the FQ than their male counterparts (n = 25), a trend reflected in typically developing (TD) children as well, suggesting that different social capabilities between men and women may impact ASD diagnosis as well (Head et al. 5). Similarly, Koenig and Tsatsanis found that females, in general, are more attuned towards social cues such as facial expressions, body language, and other nonverbal indications, citing this as a result of the differing social expectations between men and women (Kreiser and White 959). This, Head et al., and Mao et al.'s studies point to a prevalence of internalized symptoms and social camouflage, demonstrating that emotional recognition in girls with ASD may fall behind despite external social performance. For the purposes of this paper, this hypothesis will be referred to as the "social camouflage hypothesis."

Rynkiewicz et al. studied differences in emotion recognition between 5-10 year old boys and girls with clinically diagnosed ASD, using both the Faces Test and the Social Communication Questionnaire (SCQ). Girls with ASD (n = 16) scored significantly lower than boys on both the Faces Test and SCQ, according to Rynkiewicz et al. As stated by Estrin et al., these findings suggest that this is an indication of girls with ASD needing to exhibit more stereotypically severe autistic social traits (AST) in order to gain an ASD diagnosis (Estrin et al. 457). While

Head et al. suggest females with ASD may appear more socially adept, Rynkiewicz et al.'s results complicate this, showing that recognition of emotions in ASD girls may fall behind despite external social performance. Additionally, Mandy et al. examined how social traits among those with ASD developed differently between men and women, finding that 7 year old boys showed higher levels of AST than girls of the same age, yet AST declined in males and increased in females as they aged (Estrin et al. 457). Similarly to Rynkiewicz et al.'s findings, this points to the lower levels of AST among young girls as a barrier to obtaining a formal diagnosis. These results correlate to the observed trend of females being diagnosed at a later age, as they exhibit less severe ASD symptoms at a younger age (Evans et al. 3). For the purposes of this essay, this will be referred to as the "delayed AST hypothesis."

Comparing the delayed AST hypothesis with the social camouflage hypothesis seems to imply that these findings contradict each other. While inconsistent results point to a need for more research specifically on the female ASD phenotype, both hypotheses provide foundational information for further research: delayed ASD diagnosis among women and girls is directly correlated with how social expectations impact the manifestation of symptoms in females.

Due to 1) a predominant research focus on the male ASD phenotype, 2) gendered differences in AST representation and social expectations, and 3) the tendency for females to exhibit symptoms that subvert typical male presentations, existing diagnostic frameworks tend to underrepresent or misclassify autistic girls. This potentially serves as a factor contributing to ASD being more widely recognized in men, with a diagnosis ratio comparing males to females of 4.3:1. (Kreiser and White 67, Rivet and Manson 959). This diagnostic gap contributes to persistent gender disparities in early identification, access to care, and long-term support.

2.2: Machine Learning in ASD Diagnosis

In response to limitations of observation-based methods of ASD diagnosis, machine learning has emerged as a potentially more accurate diagnostic tool. As reviewed by Raj et al., machine learning as a diagnostic tool typically features classification techniques to identify parameters that yield the highest ASD diagnostic rates. Kosmickil et al. implemented ADOS into a classification model, finding that 9 out of 28 behaviors from module 2 (for nonverbal children six years or younger) and/or 12 out of 28 behaviors from module 3 (verbally fluent children to adolescents) as adequate for ASD identification (Raj et al. 996). Similarly, using the UCI machine learning repository, Ravindranath and Ra utilized a binary firefly algorithm-based feature selection wrapper, leveraging swarm intelligence, and found that differentiating 10 out of 21 features was sufficient to determine if a patient had ASD with a 92.12%-97.95% accuracy (Raj et al. 996). Meanwhile, Li et al. utilized machine learning classification algorithm RIPPER to investigate discriminative test conditions and kinematic parameters by investigating the hand movements of 16 participants with autism spectrum conditions (ASC). They found that the Va feature selection method yielded the highest sensitivity (87.3%), able to successfully detect useful patterns for ASD diagnosis, and demonstrating that machine learning is a powerful tool in ASD diagnosis given proper feature selection (Li et al. 15).

Akter et al. further explored diagnostic indicators using feature transformation and selection techniques. They found that, across all age groups, an abnormally strong interest in a specific hobby or subject (A4) and limited social adaptation (A9) were the most prominent features associated with ASD diagnosis, surpassing even age, a factor often assumed to be highly predictive (Akter et al. 166525). These findings support the social camouflage hypothesis, as males generally exhibit lower levels of social adaptation than females, making A9 more detectable in male populations.

While these studies showcase a variety of effective ML approaches across behavioral and kinematic datasets, they also present critical limitations. First, Raj et al. report that convolutional neural networks (CNNs) outperform traditional classification models, achieving

98.30% accuracy on the UCI child dataset, and suggest that earlier studies were limited by the simplicity of the models they employed (Raj et al. 1003). Second, many studies rely heavily on preexisting diagnostic tools, such as Kosmicki et al.'s use of ADOS, which embed longstanding biases toward the male ASD phenotype. Training models based on pre-existing data primarily catered towards the male ASD phenotype without accounting for biases will only continue to exacerbate the disparity between male and female ASD diagnosis rates. The next objective is to optimize machine learning to minimize implicit bias and potentially uncover novel biomarkers among the female ASD phenotype.

2.3: Interpretability and Reliance on ML

This study will utilize findings and assumptions from the book *Fairness and machine learning: Limitations and Opportunities*, written by Solon Barocas, Moritz Hardt, and Arvind Narayanan in order to establish a criteria for a model's adequate interpretability. Barocas et al. state that an overreliance on raw accuracy allows researchers to overlook unconventional manifestations of bias. Removing sensitive variables (variables that heighten potential for bias in outputs) may increase raw accuracy, but intersectional identities often allow for seemingly neutral variables to act as hosts for bias. One such example of this appears in Akter et al.'s study, in which neutral variables A4 and A9 are implicitly gendered and pose potential bias. While gender was not a prominent feature in determining ASD diagnosis, social adaptation among women could significantly lower the frequency of young girls and women exhibiting the A9 trait compared to men. Because girls often exhibit stronger social masking behaviors, they may be less likely to be flagged by these features, even if they meet criteria for ASD.

Jeon et al. caution that applying machine learning to human subjects risks undermining clinician trust due to the "black box" phenomenon, in which studies involving machine learning often lack transparency regarding predictions, allowing potential biases to go unaddressed (Jeon et al. 2). One potential way of mitigating the black box phenomenon is to minimize or acknowledge the impact that sensitive characteristics have on predictions (i.e. the trait "female" being an indicator to lower odds of ASD diagnosis). Barocas et al. proposes a criteria for non-discrimination modeling: 1) independence, in which the characteristic is statistically independent of the score, 2) separation, or equalized odds, in which prediction is made independently of trends observed in previous groups, and 3) sufficiency, in which calibration is equal amongst subgroups and prediction results actually match observed outcomes on average (Barocas et al. 55-63).

Emerging studies have examined which modeling and interpretability methods best mitigate black box concerns. Jeon et al. conducted a study utilizing 10-fold cross validation and explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) to determine model-agnostic explanation methods that yielded the most useful model explanations by experimentally applying them to several ML models (Jeon et al. 3). They found that XGBoost and GBM proved robust in predicting ASD diagnosis, with XGBoost achieving an accuracy of 0.9958 and an F1 score of 0.9924, and GBM achieving an accuracy of 0.9889 and an F1 score of 0.9924 (Jeon et al. 28). The high F1 scores are especially notable given their utility in class-imbalanced datasets, as the F1 score balances precision and recall, offering a more informative evaluation than accuracy alone.

The integration of fairness-aware algorithms and interpretable machine learning techniques presents a promising path forward, allowing researchers to begin to reduce gender disparities in ASD diagnosis. The next step is to implement models that not only predict with high accuracy but also uncover novel, bias-aware biomarkers, particularly for the underrepresented female phenotype. This dual focus on accuracy and fairness is essential to creating inclusive, ethical, and effective diagnostic tools in autism care. Utilizing findings discussed in the previous sections, this project aims to build on previous research by developing a bias-aware machine learning pipeline designed to improve early ASD diagnosis in girls.

